

Wrangel Island Nature Reserve Snow Goose Monitoring Methods October 2017

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Introduction

The population of lesser snow geese (*Anser caerulescens caerulescens*) breeding on Wrangel Island, Russia in northeast Siberia is a high priority for management shared by Russia, Canada, and the United States. Wildlife conservation agencies in these countries jointly developed a management plan for this population through the Pacific Flyway Council (2006). Monitoring of the population on the breeding grounds is a high priority task identified in the management plan. In 2017, Russian and U.S. project collaborators initiated a project to update documentation of monitoring methods at the Wrangel Island Nature Reserve. This report describes monitoring methods in place at the reserve during the 2017 breeding season.

Monitoring of snow geese colonies on Wrangel Island, Russia include annual observations and surveys on the snow goose main colony centered on the Tundra (Tundrovaya) River, and surveys of other small snow goose colonies (associated with snowy owl nests) outside of the main colony area. Observations and surveys related to environmental conditions, population status, and breeding success occur annually from May through August.

Observations and surveys on the main colony

Primary observations and surveys on the main colony estimate the ratio of yearlings (i.e. one-year old geese) and other geese in the spring population, clutch and egg size, face staining, brood size, and nesting success. An extensive annual nest transect survey is conducted after geese have left the colony. This survey provides estimates of the number and percentage of successful and unsuccessful nests, area occupied by the colony, breeding population, and average nest density. Appendix A contains information reported annually to the Pacific Flyway Study Committee.

1. Determining the proportion of yearlings and other geese in the spring population

The proportion of yearlings is determined during two periods. Results from these two surveys, combined with results of the nest survey, are used to estimate total spring population size.

The first survey is conducted following the arrival of geese on the main colony. The survey is designed to determine the proportion of yearlings in the total spring population. The survey is conducted using a spotting scope or a high quality camera with a telephoto lens, in nighttime or early

morning hours when most geese are in the colony area. The observer identifies and counts yearlings and older geese in groups within 200 m. Geese beyond 200 m are not surveyed, because yearlings with subtle gray markings can easily be misidentified as older geese (see Figure 1). The survey includes observations of at least 4,000-5,000 geese.

Figure 1. Adult (center) with two yearlings (juveniles) before molt.

The second yearling survey is conducted after the formation of the main colony when breeders are on nests, while nonbreeders are still in the colony area. Nonbreeders typically depart for molting areas between June 10-20. The survey is designed to determine the proportion of yearlings to nonbreeders (including yearlings) in the spring population. The survey occurs in nighttime or early morning hours before nonbreeders leave the colony area for feeding in the morning. Surveys are conducted at different points within and surrounding the colony, at areas where large flocks of nonbreeders are found separate from breeders (e.g. snow fields, river bottoms). The observer identifies and counts yearlings and older geese in groups within 200 m (geese beyond 200 m are not surveyed, because yearlings with subtle gray markings can easily be misidentified as older geese). The survey includes observations of several thousand geese if possible, using a spotting scope or a high quality camera with a telephoto lens. If both yearling surveys are completed correctly, the ratio obtained from the second yearling survey is always greater than or equal to the first yearling survey.

Blue phase snow geese (“blue geese”) and Ross’ geese have recently expanded their range to Wrangel Island from North American western Arctic populations. During the yearling surveys, the

proportion of blue and Ross' geese is recorded as an indicator of immigration from other populations.

[Before molting, yearling plumage differs from adults. Yearlings have gray feathers on their head, neck, back, and/or wings. Tips of yearling primaries are dark brown, while tips of adult primaries are black. Yearling bills and feet are grey/green, while those of adults are red/pink. Yearling plumage color can vary and some individuals seem to be almost all gray, while others (partially molted) are white with gray areas only on wings. Adult blue geese are easily identified by the mostly dark plumage on the body and parts of the neck, with white on the head and parts of the neck. Immature blue geese have dark plumage on most of the body. Ross' geese are similar in coloration but are much smaller than snow geese.]

2. Determining clutch size and egg size

Average clutch size and presence/absence of eggs laid on the ground indicate the amount of nesting area in the colony (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Dump nest with eggs laid on the ground.

If there are plenty of nesting areas free of snow, most breeding geese can nest. In good years, clutch size varies from 1 to 6, with an average of 3.7-4.0. In poor years with a lack of nesting areas, some geese can't find suitable nesting areas and they start laying eggs in nests of other geese or on the ground. In those years, the average clutch size could be up to 6 eggs.

The clutch size survey on the main colony occurs during incubation and is initiated after most egg laying is finished, after down appears in the most of the nests. The survey counts eggs in >1,200 active nests (>150 nests in each of the eight colony regions - see section 4 below for regions).

The number of eggs in each nest is recorded only for active nests with full clutches. Eggs in nests with full clutches are warm. In nests with big clutches (4 or more eggs) some eggs can be incubated before all eggs are laid. In addition to nests with full clutches, observers also record the number of eggs laid away from nests, number of destroyed nests, and dead geese. The main features of a nest from the current year are the presence of fresh down and feathers in the nest, and fresh goose feces near the nest. However, in some years the fresh down and feathers may be blown out of the nest by strong winds before the survey is conducted, so the presence of fresh goose feces is the best indicator of a nest from the current year (see Figure 3). If the area around the nest contains fresh feces but no eggs, the nest is recorded as destroyed. The percentage of nests with 4 eggs is used as an index to annual nesting habitat and success, and also correlates with fall / winter age ratios in the northern wintering area (British Columbia, Canada and Washington State, USA).

Figure 3. Incubating nest with fresh feces nearby.

During this survey, some nests of different types (incubating, destroyed) can be marked with flags (placed 1 m to the N) and GPS waypoints are established for these nests. The nests can be revisited later during the nest survey as a training tool to compare the appearance of different nest types after hatching.

Also during this survey, the approximate locations of nests at the edges of the colony are recorded. These nests determine the extent of transects needed for the nest survey (see below).

A special survey is conducted to measure the sizes of eggs in nests and eggs laid away from nests. Eggs from 50 nests (totaling about 200 eggs) and up to 200 eggs laid away from nests are sampled each year. All eggs are weighed and measured with calipers to determine overall length and width at the widest part. Results can provide insights into the availability of suitable nest sites, considering

the ages of geese laying eggs in and out of nests (e.g. if nest sites are limited, more older geese may lay eggs outside of nests).

3. Measuring face staining

The coloration of feathers on the faces of geese provides information regarding likely migration and wintering areas (Figure 4). Geese with red face staining have used marshes with iron in the sediments, most likely in northern coastal areas. During this survey, face staining (red, yellow, none) is determined for 500 breeding pairs. The survey can be initiated during incubation after nonbreeders have left the colony, and continues during the brood size survey (see below). Geese classified as red have a light red to deep red / rust color extending back from the bill, while those classified as white have no coloration. Geese classified as yellow have coloration ranging from light yellow to dark yellow. The survey is conducted during daytime hours using a spotting scope or binoculars, from observation points representing all colony areas. Face staining is also recorded during the brood size survey (see below).

Figure 4. Face staining (none and red).

4. Determining brood size when leaving the colony

The brood size survey begins 1-2 days after hatching starts (which is 28-32 days after the first eggs appear), when families start leaving the main colony for brood rearing areas on the Tundra of the Academy in the northern part of the island (Figure 5). The survey is conducted during several days throughout the period when families are moving to brood rearing areas. The survey determines brood size in >250-300 families and provides additional face staining data (red, yellow, none).

Figure 5. Family groups on the Tundra River moving to brood rearing areas.

This survey is conducted at hidden observation points starting in early morning throughout daytime hours, using a spotting scope or binoculars. The best observation points include the colony cabin, the east bank of the Tundra River near the cliffs close to the west slope of Peak Tundra (Pik Tundroviy), and the Peak Tundra cabin. Only families seen <100-150 m are counted, because with greater distances it is hard to determine face staining and the number of goslings in large broods (5 or more). For families with a blue goose in the pair, additional information is collected to indicate the likely sex of the blue goose and the number of blue (dark) goslings and snow goslings.

[It is very important not to disturb geese during the hatching period. Observers shouldn't be on the colony during the hatching period, because adults might leave their very young goslings that are unable to leave the nest. If this occurs, geese usually don't come back and their goslings die. Human presence on the colony during this period also has an influence on broods in the colony that have left their nests, because goslings can't run as fast as adults. These goslings will get lost and killed by predators. These are the reasons why no one is allowed on the colony during the hatching period. If there's an important reason to be on the colony, observers should stay in areas with low densities of geese or in watercourses. High density areas should be passed quickly without any stops near the nest sites – families won't go far away from nests if disturbance is minimal.]

5. Determining nesting success

The technique for conducting nest surveys on the main colony uses the method developed by E.V. Syroechkovsky (Syroechkovsky 1975) applied annually since 1969. This is the main survey conducted to estimate the total number of nests and nesting success. The survey is conducted as soon as most of the broods leave the colony.

In 2015, the technique for establishing and surveying transects was converted from the use of a compass and pacing of distances to the use of a GPS (Garmin 64s). From a central point (N 71.27177° W 179.88921°) north of confluence of the Tundra River and the Pryamoy Creek (the traditional center of the colony), east-west transects begin at this point and to the north and south of this point. Transects are separated from north to south by 0.00180 degrees latitude (corresponding to a distance of 200 m). Each east-west transect is divided into segments comprising 0.003517 degrees longitude (corresponding to a length of approximately 125 m). Each year, transects and segments are added until all nests in the colony are included in the survey area.

Currently the survey area is divided into eight regions: (see Figure 6 below):

Region Number	Region Name
1*	Left Bank, North New Area
2	Left Bank, North
3	Left Bank, South
4	Cape
5*	Southern Creek and Direct Creek, South New Area
6	Right Bank, South
7	Right Bank, North
8*	Syroechkovsky Creek and Peak Tundra Slope

Figure 6. Nest survey regions. * denotes region added in 2015 to include colony expansion areas.

Transects are walked using a GPS to maintain correct heading and identify segment boundaries. All nests are counted (successful and unsuccessful nests separately) on every 125 m segment, within an 8 m transect (4 m on each side of the east-west transect line). If transects were wider than 8 m, it would be hard to identify nests, especially in dense willow vegetation (which covers much of the colony territory). If no nests are seen within the 8 m transect but a nest is seen within 100 m of the transect line, the segment is noted with a zero and apostrophe (“0’”) and included in determining the size of the colony. When an observer is not sure whether the nest is within 4 m of the transect line, the observer puts a marker (e.g. walking stick or ski pole) on the transect line 90 degrees from the nest in question. The observer then uses a 4 m rope attached to the marker on the transect to identify the distance correctly (see Figure 7). At least 50% of the nest must be within 4 m of the transect line to be counted.

Figure 7. Accurately measuring the 4m perpendicular distance from a transect line to a nest.

As noted previously, the main features of a nest from the current year are the presence of fresh down and feathers in the nest, and fresh goose feces near the nest. However, in some years before the survey is conducted, fresh down and feathers may be blown out of the nest by strong winds or the feathers can be flattened by rain. Therefore, as noted previously, the presence of fresh goose feces is the best indicator of a nest from the current year. Current year successful nests also have at least one egg shell with a yellow or bright-orange membrane (Figure 8). Presence of a white membrane on an egg shell means that the egg was hatched in a previous year (Figure 9). If the nest area contains fresh feces but no shells, the nest was destroyed and is recorded as unsuccessful. If a nest contains cold eggs, it was abandoned and recorded as unsuccessful. All mortalities within the transect are recorded, along with any lemming nests.

Figure 8. Current year hatched eggs.

Figure 9. Nest from last year.

[Note that the survey takes a lot of time and requires concentration for many hours. It is important to hold the course of the track, to count nests in a definite width, and to record successful/unsuccessful clutches at the same time.]

This survey is used to determine the area of the colony and regions, number of nests, breeding population, nesting density, and nesting success:

Area (A) of the colony and its regions are determined by the formula: $A=nld$, where **n** is the number of segments containing nests (including 0' - segments), **l** is the length of each segment (125 m), and **d** is the distance between transects (200 m).

Number of nests (successful and unsuccessful) on the colony and its regions is calculated in two steps:

- 1) Each segment sampling area is 0.1 ha (8 m x 125 m). Combined segment sampling areas represent 4% of the total colony size (i.e. an 8 m transect is 1/25 of the 125 x 200 m segment area). The number of nests counted in each sample segment is multiplied by 25, to estimate the total number of nests in that segment area (2.5 ha).
- 2) The number of nests in all segments are summed.

Breeding population is calculated by multiplying the number of nests by 2.

Nesting density is determined by dividing the number of nests by area.

Nesting success is the percentage of total nests that were successful.

Observations and surveys of small colonies (usually associated with snowy owl nests)

Small colonies can appear in different regions of the island, usually associated with snowy owl nests. Small colonies and separate nesting pairs are common in the valleys of the Gusinaya River (1), Mamontovaya River middle part (2) and Neizvestnaya River upper and middle parts (3) – see Figure 10. Colonies are commonly found on Vesolyi Creek (a) and Sovinyi Creek (b), tributaries to the Mamontovaya River. Sometimes several thousand geese nest in these valleys.

Figure 10. Typical locations of small colonies (usually associated with snowy owl nests)

Territories where small colonies are most commonly found are checked annually. Small colonies are also recorded during the breeding snowy owl survey. Optimal dates for the small colony survey are the beginning of mass incubation to the beginning of hatching of snow goose nests. In any case, the territories of the Vesiolyi and Sovinyi creeks must be examined annually during the hatching period. Total numbers of breeding geese are recorded for each area.

Estimating the total number of geese in the spring population

The total size of the spring population is estimated each year (excluding current year production). The basic formula for total spring population size represents the sum of the breeding population and nonbreeders (including yearlings and older geese that do not nest in a given year). The proportion of yearlings and the breeding population are estimated each year using the methods described above. In the past, the total number of nonbreeders has been estimated using various methods, including visual estimates as well as calculations considering the projected age structure of the population and survival. The estimated number of nonbreeders has been added to the number of breeders estimated from the nest survey to yield the total spring population estimate each year. Thus, in a year with good breeding conditions and an older population age structure, the nest survey result gives the most accurate estimate of the total population size.

The total population size estimate is currently calculated using a formula that includes the breeding population estimates from the main colony and small colonies, the ratio of yearlings to the total spring population, and the ratio of yearlings to the total number of nonbreeders (see below and Appendix).

$$\text{total spring population} = b * y_2 / (y_2 - y_1)$$

$$\text{breeding population} = b$$

$$\text{ratio of yearlings / total population (including yearlings)} = y_1$$

$$\text{ratio of yearlings / total nonbreeders (including yearlings)} = y_2$$

Estimating the projected fall / winter juvenile percentage

Results from the brood surveys are used to estimate the total number and proportion of juveniles in the population each year. This estimate is used to predict a fall / winter age ratio, also considering the number of clutches with 4 eggs. Juveniles typically have lower survival rates than older birds, and the proportion of juveniles decreases during the year after hatch. Photo surveys in the northern wintering area indicate that the proportion of juveniles in the fall / winter population is approximately 15-20% lower than the proportion of juveniles estimated on Wrangel Island the previous summer.

Banding

Each year at least 1,000 molting geese are captured on the Tundra of the Academy using portable corral traps, as part of ongoing efforts throughout the flyways to evaluate snow goose distribution, population delineation, survival, and population size. Flightless geese are herded into traps using ATVs and walking. Banding follows U.S. Geological Survey handling and marking protocols under the supervision of biologists with adequate banding experience. Banding can be conducted in two stages on the Tundra of the Academy. When conditions allow, nonbreeders are targeted in late June or early July north from Kit Mount. Family groups are targeted in late July around the Tundra River cabin on the lower reach of the river. Bands are supplied by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Pacific Flyway Office. In addition to date, location coordinates, and band number, data collected include age (A=adult; S=second year, yearlings hatched in the previous year; and J=juvenile, hatched in the current year), sex (M, F), face stain index (1-6) assigned using a photographic key of face stains, and wintering area (S or N based on face stain index, 1-2=S, 3-6=N). In some years, additional markers are applied during banding (e.g. red neck bands).

Determining family size during departure from the island

The survey is conducted when juveniles fledge in August. The survey includes counting juveniles in separate family groups on the Tundra of the Academy or the southern coast.

Environmental Information Collected

1. Ground temperature and depth to permafrost

Beginning in 2015, an experimental site near the Peak Tundra cabin at N 71.29649 and W 179.79695 was established for measuring the ground temperature and depth to permafrost from May 20 – July 25. These indicators are important for the annual comparison of climatic conditions affecting snow goose productivity, such as progression of plant growth for foraging. For ground temperature, a data logger determines temperature automatically 8 times a day. For measuring depth to permafrost, 35 random points in snow-free areas are sampled within 20 m of the above coordinates, using a special probe pushed into the soil. Average depth is calculated for each day.

2. Wrangel Island Climate Information

A meteorological station has been in operation on Wrangel Island since 1926 at Rogers Bay, in the south part of the island near Ushokovsky. Annual temperature and precipitation data from this station are used to monitor long-term climatic trends (see <http://www.pogodaiklimat.ru>).

3. Snow Cover

Every five days from May 20 until peak nest initiation, panoramic photos (Figure 11) are taken from a standard point on top of a hill from the eastern part of the colony, with coordinates N 71.28275 W179.82446. Snow cover percentage is estimated for each colony region.

Figure 11. Example of snow cover photo taken from standard point.

Phenological Data Collected

1. Primary observations

*Arrival of the first geese on the colony – date of the first record of snow geese on the main colony region on the Tundra River.

Mass arrival – date when ~10,000 geese are on the colony.

*First nest initiation – date when the first nest is initiated. It's determined by observing eggs in nests or seeing foxes carrying eggs or seeing fresh pieces of shell, as foxes and avian predators (glaucous gulls, jaegers) eat the first eggs.

*Peak nest initiation – date when at least 50% of geese have initiated nests.

Start of incubation – date when down appears in nests on the main colony.

Departure of non-breeding birds – date when geese without nests leave the colony.

Start of hatching – date when the first goslings appear in nests. It happens 28-32 days after the date when the first eggs appear.

Mass hatching – date when about 2/3 of hatching has occurred.

Families with goslings begin leaving the colony – date when the first families leave the colony.

Most families with goslings have left the colony – date when 2/3 of families have left the colony.

Last families with goslings are left on the colony – date when <100 families are left on the colony.

*Primary data reported every year

2. Other phenological observations

By the end of the breeding season, additional phenological information may include:

First observation of snow geese on the island – the date when snow geese are first noticed on the island.

Regular observations – the date after which geese are often seen.

Beginning of departure – the date that first groups leave the island.

Mass departure – the period when most of the geese leave the island.

Last observation of snow geese on the island – the last date that geese are observed on the island.

The following phenological observations can also be gathered while working at the main regions of snow geese molting at the Tundra of Academy in July-August:

Beginning of non-breeders molt– date of first observation of molting birds (molt usually lasts 4 weeks).

Beginning of breeders molt – date of first observations of molting adult geese with goslings.

Breeders start molting within 2 weeks after goslings hatch.

First flights after molt of non-breeders – date of first observations of flights on the Tundra of the Academy.

First flights of juveniles – date of first observations of juveniles flying (usually happens 45-50 days after hatching).

Mass departure from Tundra of Academy.

Last observation of geese on the Tundra of Academy.

Literature Cited

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APPENDIX A. Wrangel Island snow goose population and productivity data

YEAR	TOTAL SPRING POP.	ADULT GEESE SPRING	% JUV SPRING	BREED POP	COLONY SIZE (HA)	NESTS	% SUCC. NESTS	CLUTCH SIZE	BROOD SIZE LV COLONY	BROOD SIZE LV ISLAND
1966								3.6		
1967								4.9		
1969				114.0	1962	58.2		3.7		
1970	150.0	120.0	20.0	120.0	2600	60.0	96.0	3.7	3.5	2.5
1971	132.0	120.0	9.1	24.0	825	12.0	55.0	4.7	3.4	2.3
1972	107.0	106.0	0.6	36.0	950	18.0	45.0	4.2	3.5	2.3
1973	86.0	85.9	0.0	12.0	200	6.0	67.0	6.0	3.9	
1974	70.0	69.5	0.7	32.0	800	15.0	0.0	4.7		
1975	56.0	56.0	0.0	56.0		28.0	74.4	3.8	3.4	2.4
1976	58.0	46.0	20.7	46.0	1840	23.0	79.0	3.7	3.2	2.8
1977	68.2	57.2	16.1	10.0	400	5.0	76.8	5.0	3.7	
1978	65.4	64.9	0.8	42.0	2200	21.0	80.0	4.2	3.7	2.4
1979	84.5	62.1	26.5	60.0	1860	30.0	90.0	3.8	3.6	
1980	90.7	80.3	11.5	20.0	315	10.0	70.0	5.4	3.3	
1981	89.0	86.2	3.2	78.0	2118	39.0	95.0	4.0	3.7	3.1
1982	100.0	81.0	18.5	28.0	688	14.0	65.0	4.1	3.2	2.8
1983	95.0	92.8	2.4	3.4	125	1.7	5.9	4.8		
1984	85.0	85.0	0.0	42.0	1500	21.0	83.3	3.7	3.2	2.1
1985	85.0	80.0	5.4	50.0	1457	25.0	87.7	3.7	3.2	2.4
1986	90.0	70.0	20.4	58.0	2100	29.0	90.0	3.9	3.6	3.2
1987	100.0	85.0	15.0	47.0	1900	23.5	80.0	3.7	3.4	2.8
1988	80.0	80.0	17.7	13.0	675	6.5	51.0	5.2	3.4	2.7
1989	70.0	70.0	1.4	60.0	1025	30.0	60.0	3.8	3.3	
1990	60.0	60.0	0.0	53.0	940	26.5	49.2	3.8	3.2	2.2
1991	60.0	56.0	6.6	41.6	888	20.8	82.0	4.1	3.4	2.7
1992	70.0	56.0	20.0	46.2	742	23.1	70.1	4.0	3.5	3.5
1993	65.0	64.5	0.8	52.2	910	26.1	85.1	3.9	3.2	
1994	70.0	52.5	25.0	30.0	1000	15.0	13.0	2.8	2.1	
1995	65.0	64.0	0.8	8.8	430	4.4	50.0	4.7	2.8	
1996	75.0	75.0	0.0	75.4	740	37.7	75.4		3.7	2.4
1997	85.0	70.0	15.0	55.2	628	22.6	71.2	4.0	3.5	
1998	90.0	80.0	10.0	31.8	750	15.9	66.0	4.6	3.5	
1999	90.0	85.0	5.6	20.8	278	10.4	75.0	4.7	3.3	
2000	95.0	87.4	8.0	49.6	738	24.8	87.8	3.5	3.2	2.8
2001	105.0	92.4	12.0	48.0	900	24.0	87.0	3.6	3.2	2.3
2002	110.0			60.6	855	30.3	81.5	4.0	3.5	3.0
2003	115.0			55.0	900	27.5	77.5			2.2
2004	117.5	111.7	4.9	56.8	838	28.4	75.0	3.6	3.2	
2005	117.5			95.8	900	47.9	82.3	4.2	3.7	3.3
2006	132.5	100.8	23.9	93.2	875	46.6	87.7	4.0	3.7	3.2
2007	140.0			79.0	1100	39.5	84.4	4.0	3.5	3.1
2008	140.0			35.0	500	10.0	35.0	4.2	2.6	
2009	132.5			108.8	1600	54.4	79.5	4.1	3.6	3.2
2010	155.0	127.0	18.0	25.0	500	8.0	43.8	3.6	2.7	
2011	150.0	144.8	3.5	143.0	1400	71.2	81.3	4.2	3.7	
2012										
2013										
2014										
2015	240.0	228.0	4.8	215.4	2680	107.7	89.1	4.0	3.7	
2016	300.0	240.0	20.0	237.0	3240	118.6	90.6	3.9	3.7	

APPENDIX B: Calculation of Total Spring Population Using Nest and Yearling Survey Results

- b = breeding population estimated from nest survey
c = number of yearlings
d = number of nonbreeders
y1 = ratio of yearlings to total spring population (including yearlings)
y2 = ratio of yearlings to nonbreeders (including yearlings)
x = total spring population

$$c/x = y_1$$

$$c = y_1(x)$$

$$c/(c+d) = y_2$$

$$c = y_2 y_1(x) + y_2(d)$$

$$y_1(x) = y_2 y_1(x) + y_2(d)$$

$$b + d = (1 - y_1)(x)$$

$$d = (1 - y_1)x - b$$

$$y_1(x) = y_2 y_1(x) + y_2(1 - y_1)x - y_2(b)$$

$$y_2(b) = y_2 y_1(x) + y_2(1 - y_1)x - y_1(x)$$

$$y_2(b) = y_2 y_1(x) + y_2(x) - y_2 y_1(x) - y_1(x)$$

$$y_2(b) = (y_2 - y_1)(x)$$

$$\mathbf{x = b * y_2 / (y_2 - y_1)}$$